

IONLOVCHI NURLARNING DOZIMETRIYASI VA XOSSALARI.

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ANNOSTATSIYA.

Maqolada ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishning dozimetriyasi ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishning xossalari, nurlanish maydonini yoki nurlanishning moddalar bilan o'zaro ta'sirini tavsiflovchi fizik miqdorlarni, shuningdek, ularni aniqlash tamoyillari va usullarini ko'rib chiqadi.

Dozimetriya kutilayotgan radiatsiya ta'siri bilan bog'liq bo'lgan jismoniy miqdorlar bilan shug'ullanadi. Bu miqdorlar odatda dozimetrik deb ataladi. O'lchangan jismoniy miqdor va kutilayotgan nurlanish effekti o'rtasidagi o'rnatilgan bog'liqlik dozimetrik miqdorlarning eng muhim xususiyatidir. Bu aloqasiz dozimetrik o'lchovlar o'z ma'nosini yo'qotadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ionlashtiruvchi nurlanish, nurlanish effekti, dozimetriya, radioaktiv manbadagi nuklid faolligi, EHM dozasi darajasi

ANNOSTATION.

In the article, dosimetry of ionizing radiation considers the properties of ionizing radiation, physical quantities describing the field of radiation or the interaction of radiation with substances, as well as the principles and methods of their determination.

Dosimetry deals with the physical quantities associated with expected radiation exposure. These quantities are usually called dosimetric. The established relationship between the measured physical quantity and the expected radiation effect is the most important feature of dosimetric quantities. Without this connection, dosimetric measurements lose their meaning.

Key words: Ionizing radiation, radiation effect, dosimetry, nuclide activity in a radioactive source, exposure dose rate

Radiatsiya ta'sirining asosiy sababi nurlangan ob'ekt tomonidan ionlashtiruvchi nurlanish energiyasining yutilishi bo'lib, so'rilgan energiya o'lchovi sifatida doza asosiy dozimetrik miqdor bo'lib chiqadi.

Dozimetriyaning eng muhim vazifasi turli muhitlarda va ayniqsa tirik organizm to'qimalarida nurlanish dozasini aniqlashdir. Buning uchun turli xil hisoblash va eksperimental usullar qo'llaniladi.

Tirik organizmga ta'sir qiluvchi nurlanish dozasini miqdoriy aniqlash, birinchi navbatda, odamlar uchun mumkin bo'lgan radiatsiyaviy xavfni aniqlash,

baholash va oldini olish uchun zarurdir. Agar gigienistlar va radiobiologlar biologik xavf nuqtai nazaridan nurlanishning maksimal ruxsat etilgan darajalari qanday degan savolga javob berishlari kerak bo'lsa, dozimetrlar bu darajalarni to'g'ri o'lchashni (aniqlashni) ta'minlashi kerak. Dozimetriyaning rivojlanishi dastlab odamlarni ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishning zararli ta'siridan himoya qilish zarurati bilan to'liq aniqlangan. Rentgen nurlanishi kashf etilgandan so'ng (1895) ko'p o'tmay, uning odamlarga zararli ta'siri aniqlandi va radiatsiyaviy xavflilik darajasini miqdoriy baholash zarurati paydo bo'ldi. Rentgen nurlarining intensivligini o'lchash uchun fotografik effekt, flüoresans, termal effekt, shuningdek kimyoviy usullar. Keyinchalik rentgen nurlanishini tavsiflovchi fizik miqdorlarni o'lchash va uning sfera bilan o'zaro ta'siri mustaqil sohaga aylandi - rentgen nurlarini o'lchash, hozirda ionlashtiruvchi nurlanish dozimetriyasining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Radiometriyada o'lchanadigan asosiy miqdorlar aniqlanib, zamonaviy dozimetriyaning deyarli barcha usullari shakllantirildi.

Dozimetrik asboblarda yordamida katta amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan ikkita asosiy turdagi o'lchovlarni amalga oshirish mumkin. Birinchi turga ta'sir qilishning butun davri davomida olingan va rentgenlarda ifodalangan nurlanishning umumiy dozasi (yoki miqdorini) o'lchash kiradi. Shaxsiy dozimetrlarga misol sifatida ion kameralari, fotografik yassi plyonkali dozimetrlar va kumush fosfat porlash printsipi bo'yicha ishlaydigan teleskopik qurilmalar kiradi. Ikkinchi turga soatiga rentgen (yoki uning fraktsiyalari) bilan ifodalangan nurlanish intensivligini o'lchash kiradi. Radiatsiya intensivligini aniqlash uchun ishlatiladigan dozimetrlarga ion kameralari, Geiger-Myuller hisoblagichlari yoki tegishli elektron va elektr o'lchash asboblari bilan birlashtirilgan sintillyatsion hisoblagichlar kiradi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Dozimetriyaning rivojlanishi dastlab odamlarni ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishdan himoya qilish zarurati bilan belgilandi. Rentgen nurlari kashf etilganidan ko'p o'tmay, insonning nurlanishidan kelib chiqadigan biologik ta'sirlar sezildi. Radiatsiyaviy xavflilik darajasini miqdoriy baholash zarurati tug'ildi. Asosiy miqdoriy mezon sifatida rentgen yordamida o'lchangan va havo ionlanishining kattaligi bilan aniqlangan ta'sir qilish dozasi qabul qilindi.

Radiyning kashf etilishi bilan radioaktiv moddalarning nurlanishi ham rentgen nurlari ta'siriga o'xshash biologik ta'sirlarni keltirib chiqarishi aniqlandi. Radioaktiv preparatlarni qazib olish, qayta ishlash va ulardan foydalanish jarayonida radioaktiv moddalarning tanaga kirishi xavfi

mavjud. Radioaktiv manbalarning faolligini (sekundiga yemirilishlar soni) o'lchash usullari ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, bu radiometriyaning asosi hisoblanadi. Radioaktiv moddaning faolligi radioaktiv modda miqdorining xarakteristikasi (vaqt birligidagi parchalanish soni). Faoliyatning tizimli birligi **Bekkerel (Bq)** - radioaktiv manbaning 1 sekundda 1 yemirilish sodir bo'lgan faolligi ($1 \text{ Bq} = 1 \text{ yemirilish/s}$). Tizimsiz birlik - **Kyuri (Ci)** - radioaktiv manbaning faolligi bo'lib, unda 1 soniyada $3,7 \times 10^{10}$ parchalanish sodir bo'ladi.

1-jadval

Asosiy nurlanish miqdorlari va ularning birliklari

Jismoniy miqdor	Birlik, uning nomi, nomi (xalqaro, ruscha)		Nisbat birliklar orasida
	tizimdan tashqari	SI	
Radioaktiv manbadagi faolligi	nuklid Kyuri (Ci, Ki)	bekkerel (Bq, Bq)	$1 \text{ Bq} = 2,7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Ci}$ $1 \text{ Ci} = 3,7 \times 10^{10} \text{ Bq}$
Radiatsiyaning ta'sir qilish dozasi	Rentgen nurlari (R, R)	Bir kg uchun kulon (C/kg, C/kg)	$1 \text{ K/kg} = 3876 \text{ R}$ $1 \text{ P} = 2,58 \times 10^4 \text{ S/kg}$
EHM dozasi darajasi	soniyada rentgen (R/s, R/s)	Amper/kg (A/Kg, A/kg)	$1 \text{ A/kg} = 3876 \text{ R/s}$ $1 \text{ R} / \text{s} \approx 2,58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ A / kg}$
So'rilgan nurlanish dozasi	Xursand (rad, xursand)	Kulrang (Gy, Gr)	$1 \text{ Gy} = 100 \text{ rad}$ $1 \text{ rad} = 0,01 \text{ Gy}$
So'rilgan doza tezligi	sekundiga rad (rad/s, rad/s)	Kulrang/sekundiga (Gy/s, Gy/s)	$1 \text{ Gy/s} = 100 \text{ rad/s}$ $1 \text{ rad/s} = 0,01 \text{ Gy/s}$
Integral nurlanish dozasi	rad·gram (rad·g, rad·g)	Joul (J, J) *	$1 \text{ J} = 10^5 \text{ rad} \cdot \text{g}$ $1 \text{ rad} \cdot \text{g} = 10^{-5} \text{ J}$
Ekvivalent nurlanish	Rem (rem, Sievert (Sv, Sv)		$1 \text{ Sv} = 100 \text{ rem}$

<i>dozasi</i>	rem)		1 rem = 0,01 Sv
<i>Dozaning ekvivalent darajasi</i>	Rem/soniya (rem/s, rem/s)	sekundiga sievert (Sv/s, Sv/s)	1 Sv/s = 100 rem/s 1 rem/s = 0,01 Sv/s

* 1 Gy, ta'rifiga ko'ra, har bir kilogramm uchun 1 Joul bo'lganligi sababli, integral dozaning SI birligi Grey·kilogramm Joulga aylantiriladi.
(1 Gy·kg = 1 (J/kg)·kg = 1 J).

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR

Radiatsiya terapiyasida radiatsiya xavfsizligining zaruriy sharti - bu xodimlar va radiatsiya ta'siriga uchragan bemorlar tomonidan so'rilgan nurlanish energiyasining aniq miqdoriy hisobidir.

AI miqdorini aniqlash uchun "doza" tushunchasi qo'llaniladi. AI dozasi - bu nurlanish energiyasining nurlangan moddaning massasi yoki hajmiga nisbati. Klinik dozimetriyada quyidagi tushunchalar qo'llaniladi:

Radiatsiyaning ta'sir qilish dozasi - tarqaladigan jismlar bo'lmaganda quruq (erkin) havoda o'lchanadigan nurlanish dozasi. U asosan nurlanish manbasini (uning kuchi, parametrlarining doimiyliigi va boshqalar) tavsiflaydi. Ta'sir qilish dozasi faqat energiya 3 MeV dan oshmaydigan ionlashtiruvchi nurlanish uchun qo'llaniladi.

Ta'sir qilish dozasining tizimdan tashqari birligi Rentgen - bu rentgen yoki γ nurlanish dozasi bo'lib, u normal sharoitda (0° S va bosim 1 atmosfera) 1 sm^3 havoda 1 e ga teng zaryad hosil qiladi. Bilan. e) statik elektr (har bir belgining $2,08 \times 10^9$ juft ionlari).

Sida ta'sir qilish dozasini o'lchash birligi kg uchun kulon - bu normal sharoitda 1 kg havoda 1 kulonga teng zaryad hosil bo'lgan rentgen yoki γ nurlanish dozasidir.

Xuddi shu dozani turli vaqt oraliq'ida berish mumkin. Shuning uchun doza tezligi tushunchasi kiritiladi - vaqt birligi uchun hisoblangan doza. Ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishning biologik ta'siri ham dozaga, ham uning kuchiga bog'liq.

So'rilgan nurlanish dozasi ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishning nurlangan to'qimalarga ta'sirining asosiy miqdoriy ko'rsatkichidir. U nurlanish jarayonida nurlangan moddaning massa birligiga to'g'ri keladigan energiya miqdori bilan aniqlanadi. So'rilgan doz har qanday turdagi ionlashtiruvchi nurlanish uchun

qo'llaniladi. So'rilgan dozaning SI birligi J/kg. Bu qiymat deyiladi " Grey " (Gr) . 1 Gy - ionlashtiruvchi nurlanish dozasi, bunda 1 kg nurlangan moddada 1 J ga teng energiya yutiladi.. Yutilgan dozaning tizimdan tashqari birligi rad. 1 rad - nurlanish dozasi, bunda 1 g nurlangan moddada 100 ergga teng energiya so'riladi.

Biologik ob'ektlarni nurlantirishda bir xil yutilgan dozada turli xil ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishlar turli xil biologik ta'sirga ega bo'lganligi sababli, "ekvivalent nurlanish dozasi" tushunchasi mavjud. Muayyan turdagi nurlanish natijasida yuzaga keladigan biologik ta'sirlar 200 keV energiyali foton nurlanishi natijasida hosil bo'lgan effekt bilan taqqoslanadi.

Insonning surunkali ta'sirida (past dozalarda) nurlanishning ma'lum bir turi uchun radiatsiya xavfi foton nurlanishiga qaraganda necha marta yuqori ekanligini ko'rsatadigan koefitsient (teng so'rilgan dozada 200 keV) sifat omili deb ataladi. (QC). Foton nurlanishi uchun $KK = 1$. a-zarralar uchun $KK = 20$, protonlar va tez neytronlar uchun $KK = 10$, termal neytronlar uchun $KK = 2,5-3$. QC qiymati ma'lum turdagi nurlanishning LET ga bog'liq. LET qanchalik baland bo'lsa, hujayraning shikastlanishi shunchalik katta bo'ladi va tiklanish qobiliyati shunchalik past bo'ladi. Shunday qilib, bir xil so'rilgan dozada protonlar bilan nurlanishning zararli (yoki terapevtik) ta'siri foton nurlanishiga qaraganda 10 baravar ko'p bo'ladi.

Ushbu nurlanishning QC ni hisobga olgan holda tirik ob'ekt tomonidan qabul qilingan doza **ekvivalent doza** deb ataladi . Ekvivalent doza so'rilgan dozani va Aning biologik ta'sirini hisobga oladi. "Ekvivalent doza" tushunchasi faqat radiatsiya xavfini baholash uchun ishlatiladi.

Hozirgi vaqtda barcha holatlarda SI birliklarida ifodalangan jismoniy miqdorlardan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi.

Ionlashtiruvchi nurlanishning dozimetriya usullari

Aida hid, ta'm yoki odamga ularni ro'yxatdan o'tkazish imkonini beradigan boshqa xususiyatlar yo'q. Aning miqdoriy va sifat xususiyatlarini o'lchash uchun nurlanishning materiya bilan o'zaro ta'sirining ta'sirini ro'yxatga olish asosida turli usullar qo'llaniladi.

Dozimetrler AI dozasini yoki doza tezligini o'lchash uchun mo'ljallangan asboblardir. Ushbu qurilmalar Aning materiya bilan o'zaro ta'siridan kelib chiqadigan ionlanish, sintilatsiya, fotografik, kimyoviy va boshqa effektlarni ro'yxatga olish va miqdoriy baholashga asoslangan.

Dozimetrlarning asosiy guruhlari:

Klinik - ishchi nurda Alni o'lchash uchun. Radiatsion terapiyaga tayyorgarlik ko'rishda va nurlanish jarayonida qo'llaniladi.

Himoya nazorati uchun dozimetrlar - ish joylarida tarqalgan nurlanishning doza tezligini o'lchash uchun (radiatsiyaviy xavfsizlik tizimida). Ushbu dozimetrlar to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'qilishi kerak.

Individual - AI sohasida ishlaydigan shaxslarning ta'sirini nazorat qilish.
Dozimetriya usullari:

Biologik - to'qimalarda II ning ma'lum dozasi (eritemal doza, epilasyon dozasi, o'ldiradigan doz) bilan nurlanganda yuzaga keladigan reaksiyalarni baholashga asoslangan. Ular indikativ bo'lib, asosan eksperimental radiobiologiyada qo'llaniladi.

Kimyoviy - nurlanish ta'sirida ma'lum moddalarda sodir bo'ladigan qaytarilmas kimyoviy reaksiyalarni qayd etishdan iborat (radiokimyoviy usul, fotografik usul).

Radiokimyoviy usul - II (Fe^{2+} Fe^{3+}) ta'sirida qora temirning uch valentli oksidlanishiga asoslangan, bu rangning o'zgarishiga (shaffoflik) olib keladi. Ferrosulfat dozimetrlari qo'llaniladi. Ushbu dozimetrlarning diapazoni juda katta (20 dan 400 Gy gacha) bo'lgani uchun ular faqat favqulodda vaziyatlarda qo'llaniladi.

Fotosurat usuli - IQ ta'sirida rentgen plyonkasining qorayishi sodir bo'ladi, uning darajasi nurlarning yutilgan energiyasiga proporsionaldir. Qora rangning zichligi nurlanish dozasini aniqlash uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Ushbu usulning kamchiliklari dozimetr ko'rsatkichlarining nurlanishning sifatli tarkibiga bog'liqligidir. Dozani aniqlashning aniqligi past. Plyonkali dozimetrlar yordamida radiatsiya terapiyasi asboblarida yorug'lik va nurlanish maydonlari o'rtasidagi muvofiqlikni aniqlash qulay.

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